

Meaningful interaction of users with product shapes

Wellington Gomes de Medeiros, Universidade Federal de Campina Grande/CNPq;
Staffordshire University, Faculty of Arts, Media and Design, Flaxman Building, College
Road, Stoke-on-Trent ST4 2DE, United Kingdom, w.g.medeiros@staffs.ac.uk,
wg.medeiros@uol.com.br

Philippa Ashton, Bath School of Art and Design, Sion Hill, Bath BA1 5SF, United Kingdom,
p.ashton@bathspa.ac.uk

Type of contribution: research paper

Key conference theme: Semantics

Abstract

This paper describes an ongoing study, which aims to explore the concept of Meaningful Interaction (MI) as a proposition and a framework for investigating and analysing the semantics of interactions of people with artefacts. First, the main five aspects of MI are defined: (1) a dialogical process of communication/collaboration between people, artefacts and context at the semantic level; (2) a combination of actions between the three active factors (artefacts, users and contexts) in user's cognitive behaviour; (3) the quality of interaction as conveying meanings or implications in users behaviours; (4) the addition of meanings as values to user's life; and (5) a framework for clustering and analysing data which illuminates the semantics of interaction. Then, the paper describes an empirical study which investigates how the configuration of some products shapes may trigger MI with male users at the pragmatic and emotional levels. The paper concludes by stressing the importance of devising specific tools to access MI, and outlines some additional issues required to investigate the proposition further.

Key words: Meaningful Interaction, semantics, emotion, products shapes

Introduction

This paper refers to an ongoing research that aims to contribute to the understanding of interactions of users with artefacts at the semantic level. It explores the role of some products shapes in triggering meanings during the interactions that provoke users' pragmatic and emotional responses. First, the paper briefly reviews the context in which semantics and emotion are informing new design paradigms. Then it describes the term Meaningful Interaction (MI)¹ as a proposition for exploring semantic issues and analysing users' responses and behaviour during product interaction. This proposition is mainly based on the emergent thinking that the features of artefacts and contexts of interaction have semantic properties. The meanings triggered during interaction may elicit specific responses and the study shows that these are broadly in pragmatic (practical and critical) and emotional (ideological and ludic) dimensions. The paper also describes empirical study which attempts to show how some products shapes trigger semantic associations in male users, and presents further avenues for studies which will consolidate MI as a concept.

Context of the study: design, semantics and emotion

Since the term *product semantics* was proposed to define qualities of products in which embodied meanings have an important role in establishing interactions (Krippendorff & Butter, 1984), design researchers have sought to fully understand the relationship between semantics and design. As a result, designers should consider carefully the role that embodied meanings in artefacts have in the user's life in order to use semantic meanings to inform the design process. Despite several key studies, the issues surrounding semantics and design have not yet been satisfactorily investigated and certainly in order that designers can benefit. One of the main concerns is the lack of a clear understanding of the qualities of product features which elicit meanings that can trigger specific reactions. Few publications have reported theoretical and empirical approaches on this subject (Green & Jordan, 2002; McDonagh *et al.*, 2004).

¹ The acronym MI will be used to avoid successive repetitions of the term Meaningful Interaction. The term meaningful interaction is mainly found in Social-Psychology publications. In the design field it is vaguely used to refer to interactions mainly with virtual products and sometimes with material products. This study depicts this term as a proposition to stress the interactions with physical products by breaking the relationships between users and artifacts into four semantic values.

In this debate on semantics, the relationship between usability and emotion is no longer deemed as purely opposite or vaguely related. In the search to define interaction beyond usability, some studies present different views on interactions (Hummels, 2005; Zuo *et al.*, 2004; Kuusela *et al.*, 2005; Zimmerman *et al.*, 2005; Sonneveld, 2004). A review of published papers reveals studies mainly into emotional responses and interaction with virtual products (Wensveen, 2005). Hence, the emotional reaction of users to physical shapes still requires research (Hauge-Nilsen & Flyte, 2002; Crothers *et al.*, 2004). Despite empirical evidence which highlighted that ‘form plays a critical role in allowing people to talk about their relationships to products’ (Forlizzi *et al.*, 2003), the meaningful dimension of product form remains a fertile ground for investigation.

One of the most debatable topics is the confrontation of the boundaries between usability and emotional qualities in products. However, if considered under the umbrella of semantics, these two aspects of design should be understood more as complementary rather than opposite. The association between usability and emotion is very important even for functional-based products such as packaging (Woodcock *et al.*, 2004). People may feel attached or detached from products for reasons others than its functional properties (Savas, 2004), presupposing that products carry a broad possibility of meanings that may generate, for instance, pleasurable interactions (Jordan, 2002). The MI proposition moves forward the debate on design, semantics and interaction by exploring the possibility of meanings within four semantic values: practical and critical (pragmatic dimension), and ideological and ludic (emotional dimension). As semantics and emotion arise as a paradigm for design (Krippendorff, 2006), the Meaningful Interaction proposition seeks to contribute for this field.

Recent studies propose that male consumption and behaviour is shifting towards a more emotional and sensitive response (Salzman *et al.*, 2005). Hence, the empirical study described here explores the role of the MI of male users in relation to packaging shapes.

Meaningful Interaction (MI)

MI can be summarised as encompassing the following characteristics:

1. It is a dialogical process of communication/collaboration between the elements of interactions (people, artefacts and contexts) in a dynamic relationship at the semantic level.
2. It is a combination of actions between the three elements, where each one has an active role (at the semantic level) in the user’s cognitive behaviour through their semantic qualities.

3. It accesses the symbolic properties of interactions that add meanings as values (significance or purpose) to user's life, such as those meanings in artefacts playing roles in the (re)construction of users' identities, such as taste and lifestyle.
4. It ascribes four semantic values to the interactions: practical and critical at the pragmatic dimension, and ideological and ludic at the emotional dimension².
5. MI offers a systematic framework to unveil the implicit meanings or implications that may or may not be explicitly expressed by the users during interactions (Fig. 1).

Figure 1, the MI semantic framework and the semantic values.

The four semantic values of MI

As shown in Figure 1, the four MI semantic values are: practical and critical (pragmatic dimension); ideological and ludic (emotional dimension). The pragmatic dimension stresses those denotative meanings which artefacts provoke. Conversely, the emotional dimension is

² Jean-Marie Floch proposes a semiotic grid as a model for understanding meanings and narratives in commercial signs. He describes two categorical distinctions of values: the use values and the basic values; and four types of valorisation: the practical, the utopian, the ludic and the critical (Floch, 2000: 118). This study recognises that users may establish semantic associations during interactions at similar levels of values proposed by Floch.

less strict than the pragmatic values, as it covers many possibilities of meanings apart those pragmatic.

The four semantic dimensions are described as follows:

1. The *practical semantic values* cover those semantic associations connected mainly to the physical attributes of the products. The users' understanding of shapes, colours, textures, and other material features trigger semantic associations such as stable, proportioned and others.
2. The *critical semantic values* reveal judgments and associations related to how the users actually feel (and think) about a product. Meanings such as comfortable and functional are critical values.
4. The *ideological semantic values* imply semantic associations underpinned by symbolic paradigms embodied in products. Products that represent social paradigms, status or identity have symbolic meanings as primary reference for users. Meanings such as fashionable, male, and traditional illustrate how users aggregate ideological values in products.
5. The *ludic semantic values* are about individual reactions and preferences rather than social or symbolic patterns of behaviour. At this level, the meanings translate somehow the possibility of playfulness in interactions and reflect a sort of 'state-of-spirit' and mood of the users. Semantic associations such as funny, cute and boring may expose the user's feelings.

Empirical study: the MI of male users with packaging shapes

Aiming to explore empirically the MI proposition, this study investigates the MI of men with particular shapes. Current thinking suggests that there is likely to be a shift in the way contemporary male users interact with products as a result of more overt sensitive attitudes and behaviour (Crozier, 1994; Levant, 1996). Hence, the assumption that men place greater emphasis upon instrumental and use-related meanings in the relationships with products should be reviewed.

In order to verify the MI of male users with shapes, an exploratory study was undertaken based on tests with 44 men. The main objectives of the tests were: to identify how some existing shapes with different configurations trigger semantic associations in male users during interactions, to scrutinise the qualities of shapes in activating the responses of male users and to test and review the MI proposition and the means by which it can be studied. The results of this empirical study will inform this exploratory view on the role of shapes in MI.

The tests were carried out under laboratory conditions at the Staffordshire University, in UK. The study is now in the final stages of analysis, but the sample profile, the shapes tested and the first results are presented briefly as follows.

Sample Profile

The purpose of the experiments was to investigate means by which MI could be robustly tested. It was recognised that the very nature of semantic analysis suggested that the particular background and attitudes of individual respondents would impact on their choices. Furthermore, as individual and socially constructed frameworks are subject to change, so choices may be transient. A very large sample would be needed to provide data which would show actual responses across a wide population. It was important therefore to select a sample that had meaning and could be related to the notion of societal values and change.

The sample was opportunistically selected by invitation, from Staffordshire University and the surrounding area. In total, 44 men aged between 18 and 60 years old took part in the tests (Table 1). As the tests were carried out on the university campus, students, lecturers and teaching/research professionals were heavily represented in the participant group.

	Ages	Age groups	Total per age group
Participant per age group	18, 19	> 20	2
	20, 21 (2), 22 (5), 23, 24, 25	20-25	11
	29 (2)	26-30	2
	31 (4), 33(2), 35	31-35	7
	36 (3), 37 (2), 40 (2)	36-40	7
	42, 43 (2), 45	41-45	4
	46, 48, 49 (2)	46-50	4
	52 (2), 55	51-55	3
	56, 58, 60	56-60	3
	63	< 60	1
Total			44

Table 1, participants' age distribution.

Products shapes for testing

As this empirical study focuses on how men react to particular shapes, care was taken to select particular types of shapes. The shapes for test were selected from existing packaging and function did not have a strong impact on the choice, but a range of different shapes were required. The objective was to verify how the participants would react to three types of shapes (Figure 2): predominantly organic/curved (shapes 1, 2 and 3), predominantly geometric (shapes 4 and 5) and hybrid shapes (neither predominantly organic nor geometric) (shapes 6 and 7). Existing packaging was used because there is a large variety of products shapes in the market with which people interact daily. Creating shapes would not reflect real situations of interaction – they would not be ‘real’ products for the testers. The design of packaging for male grooming products is now more sophisticated and seems to explore shapes that are at the boundaries of functionality and aesthetics. The test shapes were therefore products for personal care (Figure 2): (1 and 7) shower gel, (2) powder, (3) shower gel/shampoo, (4) moisturising, (5) perfume, and (6) shampoo. In order to diminish the influence of colours, printed texts and pictures on the respondents, the packs were painted grey which is a colour often associated with this product area.

Figure 2, products shapes used for the tests.

Research method

The tests were divided into two sections: video observation with interview and questionnaire. In this way, each respondent would have three sets of data (video, interview and questionnaire) relating to each shape. This method was arrived at after several pilot test processes where different variants of the method were trialled. The tests took an average of 20 minutes per participant and were mounted in a room set up specially for the tests. First, each participant was asked to interact with the shapes whilst the researcher asked five open

questions related to the four values which are presented below. The testers were videoed during this part of the experiment.

Question 1 (practical and critical): *choose two shapes you feel are most practical for grasping and handling, and say why.*

Question 2 (ludic): *choose two shapes you find most enjoyable and two others you find least enjoyable and say why.*

Question 3 (ideological): *which two shapes do you feel could reflect your lifestyle or personality? Say why.*

Question 4: *select from the group those shapes which you feel perform a mainly practical function. Say why.*

Question 5: *select from the group those shapes which you feel perform a mainly emotional function. Say why.*

In the second part of the test the participants completed a semantic differential questionnaire. Twenty bipolar adjectives (five for each of the four semantic values) identified through previous pilot tests, were displayed for each shape (Table 2). Each shape was rated for its place between the paired adjectives on a seven-point scale.

Pragmatic Dimension		Emotional Dimension	
Practical bipolar items	Critical bipolar items	Ideological bipolar items	Ludic bipolar items
Steady-Unsteady	Functional-Not	Unique-Common	Cute-Not Cute
Solid-Soft	Functional	Male-Female	Exciting-Boring
Geometric-Organic	Comfortable-	Modern-Traditional	Attractive-Unattractive
Proportioned-Not	Uncomfortable	Peculiar-Normal	Friendly-Unfriendly
Proportioned	Usable-Unusable	Fashionable-	Serious-Funny
Balanced-Not Balanced	Simple-Complex	Unfashionable	
	Pleasant-Unpleasant		

Table 2, the bipolar adjectives found through pilot tests.

The third part of the questionnaire asked participants to correlate each shape to four given structured statements related to the four semantic values:

I would express my response to this shape in emotional terms such as: attractive, serious, exciting, unpleasant, and others similar (ludic).

I would express my response to this shape in terms that relate to using it, such as: comfortable, unfriendly, usable, and others similar (critical).

I would express my response to this shape in terms that relate to its physical attributes such as: steady, unbalanced, soft, proportioned, and others similar (practical).

I would express my response to this shape in terms of ideas such as: fashionable, traditional, male/female, unique, and others similar (ideological).

Summary of the questionnaire findings

The data was analysed for group norms and to establish individual differences within the group. A pattern of interaction response relating to socio-economic factors and usage of men's grooming products was also sought. Some of these analyses are still to be completed. Some of the key results of data analysis are presented. Table 3 presents the most likely semantic values experienced per shape by the group, the most representative individual's choices within the group and the group's responses to the statements.

Responses	Shape 7						
Group's Choices	Critical Ideological	Critical	Critical Ideological	Practical	Critical Ludic	Practical Critical Ideological	Critical
Individuals' Choices	Practical	Ideological Ludic	Ludic	Practical Critical	Ludic	Critical	Practical Critical
Statements	Critical	Critical	Critical	Ideological	Ludic	Practical	Ideological

Table 3, the most likely semantic values experienced per shape by the participants.

As shown in Table 3, the data from observations, correlated with the questionnaire responses, indicates that the configuration of **shape 1** appears to trigger meanings in the critical, practical and ideological domains. Probably because of its organic form - with indentations that indicate how to grasp it - it denotes mainly critical understanding. This shape tends to reflect contemporary concepts for product design, as it was described by the testers as peculiar, fashionable and strongly related to masculinity (ideological value). On the other hand, it also triggers ideas which somehow suggest analogies with gadgets, as the users described it in the video.

Shape 2 triggers mainly critical values. Despite not as indexical³ as shape 1, its organic configuration indicates ways of handling and how people may feel by using it. On the other hand – as found in the individuals' responses - this shape also triggers ideological values such as unique, common, female, traditional, normal, unfashionable; and mainly negative ludic values, such as not cute, boring, unattractive and unfriendly. This shape performed mainly negative MI.

The analysis shows that **shape 3** may trigger a broad variety of meanings at the four levels of MI. Yet, comparing the three test sections, it is more likely to trigger critical, ideological and ludic meanings. It provokes a plethora of meanings, causing some sort of confusing on both pragmatic and emotional levels. Its soft curved configuration and its complex and obscure system of use did not provoke straight positive responses.

Despite the responses to the statements suggesting that **shape 4** generates ideological meanings, the analysis proved that it is more likely to trigger first practical and then critical meanings. This make this shape the most pragmatic over the seven shapes tested. Its geometric and minimalist configuration provokes meanings that trigger ideas related mainly to its physical features and then to its potential for using and handling. At the ideological level, this shape was mainly described as *male* by the testers.

Shape 5 is very effective to establishing ludic interactions. The analysis of the three test sections shows the effectiveness of this shape at the ludic semantic level. The testers did play with this shape. Also the participants constantly emphasised its aesthetic qualities. As shape 4, it is geometric, but its spherical configuration immediately communicates meanings that made the testers think on objects that resemble playfulness and gadgets. This shape was very welcome by the participants.

Shape 6 is very effective in communicating practical and critical values. Yet, its configuration triggers ideological values. The groups' responses show that somehow they understand this shape equally at the three levels. In spite of its hybrid configuration provoked confusing to the groups, the individuals responded clearly to some of the meanings it triggered.

³ Index is one of the Peircean models of signs 'in which the signifier is not arbitrary but is directly connected in some way (physically or causally) to the signified' (Chandler, 2003: 37).

Shape 7 triggered mainly practical, critical and ideological values. However, the analysis of the groups' responses shows that it is not as effective in triggering ideological meanings as shape 6. Nevertheless, the reactions to the statements show that some individuals strongly see this shape at the ideological level.

Summary of the video findings

The video observation and interview aimed to gather data mainly on the adjectives and meaningful associations that the participants would express freely without the bipolar adjectives as stimulus; the actions taken during the interaction with the shapes and how these actions are used to emphasize the semantic associations. The products were displayed for each participant in similar layout. Analysis of the video footage involved identifying actions and words used and placing these in one of the four semantic domains in the MI framework.

A first analysis of the semantic associations articulated freely by the subjects, shows that they expressed a considerable number of associations. Figure 3 shows that the most of the semantic associations are at the practical domain followed by the ideological, critical and ludic domains. The results indicate that in this particular test, the pragmatic dimension of values (practical and critical values) had a primary impact on the male's reactions. The denotative meanings with practical and critical values exceeded the connotative meanings which are related to emotional dimensions. Nevertheless, the ideological values - which are at the opposite side of the practical values in the MI framework (Figure 1) - triggered a significant number of expressed associations. This result points to the likelihood that for this test, male users MI would tend to value pragmatic dimensions, but they also express significant ideological values too. This result supports the findings from the questionnaires as already presented here, and is significant when we take into account that the products tested are packaging, which are designed to have high functionality.

Figure 3, the semantic associations according to the four semantic values.

The video analysis provides further evidence of the MI of the male respondents by combining the above semantic associations with patterns of actions. It was observed that certain gestures and body expressions were used to emphasise some of the semantic associations. This information is useful for the purpose of this study as it depicts how the participants actually behave when expressing the semantic associations. Moreover, it provides the data to identify those reactions which are subtle or tacit, as sometimes the action itself was the only possible form of expression. A pilot analysis identified the following main actions (not necessarily in this sequence): approaching, grasping, inspecting closely, inspecting at a distance, comparing, making analogies, having fun, trying out and tactile inspection. Each action was clustered according to the semantic associations expressed during the interactions (Figure 3). It was observed that the subjects used more variations of body expression when making practical and critical valorisations. However, the emotions manifested on the faces were more demonstrative when subjects verbalized associations such as friendly, funny, boring and pleasant, which are adjectives at the ludic domain.

Figure 4, patterns of behaviours and actions to emphasise the semantic associations: (1) approaching, (2) comparing, (3) inspecting closely, (4) making analogies, (5) inspecting at a distance, (6) having fun, (7) grasping, (8) trying out, (9) tactile inspection.

Taking into account the relationship between the verbalized semantic associations and the body and facial expressions, the video demonstrates that the pragmatic dimension of the shapes (practical and critical) is the most significant in triggering reactions. For associations at the practical level, the main actions identified were: inspecting at a distance, approaching, grasping and the tactile inspection; for the critical values: grasping, inspecting closely, and trying out; for the ideological values: comparing and making analogies; for the ludic values: having fun and making analogies. This indicates that during this test, despite participants frankly manifested emotions at the ludic level, they tend to be more excited when expressing impressions about the shapes at the practical level, where they make comments about the physical qualities of the shapes.

Main actions at the practical level	Main actions at the critical level	Main actions at the ideological level	Main actions at the ludic level

Figure 5, main actions per semantic value.

Conclusions

The primary findings of this research indicate that the MI proposition is a manageable and useful proposition for unveiling issues on pragmatic and emotional interactions with product shapes. The empirical study points to the effectiveness of the four values as a device for systematic clustering and analysing interactions. The juxtaposition of the semantic values, underpinned by the denotative and connotative dimensions of meanings, offers helpful directions for the conversion of users' verbal expressions and actions into useful information. The combination of structured questionnaire, open questions in interview and video-observation proved effective to accessing the participants' responses and actions.

In this particular empirical study, the results from the questionnaire and the interview/video observation show that male MI tends to be primarily in the practical domain, and then at the critical level. This indicates that the product shapes tested here tend to trigger reactions predominantly based on their physical qualities, and secondly on their functional qualities. As the shapes tested was packaging, this may be partially explained as a consequence of the functional nature of this particular product. Nevertheless, it was found that the participants have considerable emotional reactions, firstly at the ideological level and then at the ludic level. This result points to the assumption that even those very functional-based products may trigger men's meaningful associations and reaction at both pragmatic and emotional dimensions. In spite of the early stage and exploratory nature of this research, these findings move forward the current thinking that products embody both emotional and functional meanings and also accords with the view that contemporary groups of men are susceptible to both domains.

This study has pointed to some further questions that should be carefully investigated, such as the reasons why some shapes provoke specific associations in male users. It is also important to explore different kinds of products attributes to verify if the pragmatic based values are actually the most dominant - with regard to male users' responses - than the emotional based values. The tests described in this study were carried out under laboratory conditions based on stimulus through product interaction, interviews and questionnaire. Future work on this subject should consider the possibility of investigating MI in real contexts where people naturally interact with products. Since this study concentrated on product shapes, all the graphic and visual information was obliterated, forcing subjects to concentrate on the shapes.

However, this procedure should be handled carefully as users interact with the whole attributes of products. Hence, upcoming work should also take into account the study of MI of users with products as they are actually found and used.

References

Crozier, R. (1994) *Manufactured Pleasures*. Manchester: Manchester University Press.

Crothers, S. E. W.; Clarke, R. B.; Montgomery, J. A. I. (2004) "The Development of Empirical Techniques for the Investigation of Design Perception." In McDonagh, D., Hekkert, P., Erp, J., Guy, D. (eds) *Design and Emotion*. London: Taylor & Francis, 426-430.

Floch, J. (2000) *Visual identities*. London: Continuum.

Forlizzi, J., Gemperle, F. & Disalvo, C. (2003) "Perceptive Sorting: a Method for Understanding Responses to Products", DPPI'03, June 23-26, 103-108.

Green, W. S., Jordan, P. W. (eds) (2002) *Pleasure with Products: Beyond Usability*. London: Taylor & Francis.

Hauge-Nilsen, A.; Flyte, M. G. (2002) "Understanding Attributes that contribute to Pleasure in Product Use." In Green, W. S., Jordan, P. W. (eds) *Pleasure with Products: Beyond Usability*. London: Taylor & Francis, 257-270.

Hummels, C. (2005) "Descendants of a Design Quest for Diversity." In Wensveen, S. (ed) *Proceedings of the Conference Designing Pleasurable Products and Interfaces*. Eindhoven, 13-26.

Jordan, P. (2002) "The Personalities of Products". In Green, W. S., Jordan, P. W. (eds.): *Pleasure with Products: Beyond Usability*. London: Taylor & Francis, 20-47.

Krippendorff, K., Butter, R. (1984) "Products Semantics: Exploring the Symbolic Qualities of Form." In *The Journal of the Industrial Designers Society of America*. Spring: 4-9.

Krippendorff, K. (2006) *The Semantic Turn*. New York: Taylor & Francis.

Kuusela, K., Koshinen, I., Bataarbee, K., Soronen, A., Mayra, F., Mikkonen, J. (2005) "Pragmatic Aesthetics as a Design Resource for Proactive Information Technology." In

Wensveen, S. (ed) *Proceedings of the Conference Designing Pleasurable Products and Interfaces*. Eindhoven: Technische Universiteit, 297-313.

Levant, R. F. (1996) "The New Psychology of Men." In *Professional Psychology: Research and Practice*, Vol. 27(3): 259-265.

McDonagh, D., Hekkert, P., Erp, J., Guy, D. (eds) (2004) *Design and Emotion*. London: Taylor & Francis.

Salzman, M.; Matathia, I.; O'Reilly, A. (2005) *The Future of Men*. New York: Palgrave.

Savas, O. (2004) "A Perspective On The Person-Product Relationship: Attachment And Detachment." In McDonagh, D., Hekkert, P., Erp, J., Guy, D. (eds) *Design and Emotion*. London: Taylor & Francis, 317-321.

Sonneveld, M. (2004) "Dreamy Hands: Exploring Tactile Aesthetics in Design." In McDonagh, D., Hekkert, P., Erp, J., Guy, D. (eds) *Design and Emotion*. London: Taylor & Francis, 228-232.

Wensveen, S. (ed.) (2005) *Proceedings of the conference Designing Pleasurable Products and Interfaces*. Eindhoven: Technische Universiteit Eindhoven.

Woodcock, A.; Torrens, G.; McDonagh, D. (2004) "Emotional Responses To Food Packaging." In McDonagh, D., Hekkert, P., Erp, J., Guy, D. (eds), London: *Design and Emotion*. Taylor & Francis, 308-313.

Zimmerman, J.; Hurst, A. K.; Peeters, M. M. R. (2005) "Fabric-circle-slider: Prototype Exploring the Interaction Aesthetics of Conceptual Integration." In Wensveen, S. (ed.): *Proceedings of the Conference Designing Pleasurable Products and Interfaces*. Eindhoven: Technische Universiteit, 271-282.

Zuo, H.; Hope, T.; Jones, M.; Castle, P. (2004) "Sensory Interaction with Materials." In: McDonagh, D., Hekkert, P., Erp, J., Guy, D. (eds) *Design and Emotion*. London: Taylor & Francis, 223-227.